

Quantum photon theory

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1 Introduction

What if all elementary particles were made up of photons, and all electromagnetic fields were curvature in space? Let's start by what we know of photons, we know they have a finite speed as C , we also know that photons has 0 mass, carries electromagnetic fields, can have different frequencies, and always moves at C relative to all observers.

2 Applying

Let's question this hypothesis claim to its limits, and solidify it:

- If photons were the building blocks of elementary particles, why should they bend space?
- Why should space bend the way it bends??
- How would this hypothesis' logic predict electromagnetic forces?
- Why do elementary particles have inertia?

2.1 If photons were the building blocks of elementary particles, why should they bend space?

Let's answer our first question, if elementary particles made up of photons can bend space into another dimension, that means all photons should share 1 line, but how can even a photon move in that new dimension to begin with? If we assume that photons rotates a fixed angle at random intervals of time, then our hypothesis would predict that photons moving at maximum speed in space rotate rarely, but photons with mass are rotating very frequently, in other words lagging at its position. Let us try to describe this photon movement with an equation with the following variables:

- b (random variable controlling the interval between rotations)
- r (unknown constant variable controlling rotation)
- a (current photon's angle)
- P (an even controlled variable, the bigger, the better)
- k (controlled variable for accuracy)
- C (speed of light)
- X, Y, Z, W (dimension variables)

First let us define a function of time to output how many intervals has been completed: $f(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{t}{b}} (\cos(\frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{\pi n}{b}))^p$

What this function does is output a prediction how many intervals has been completed, so $\cos(x)$ can only equal 1, or a number close to 0, since it's raised to the power of P, and taking the sum of this series, we will know how many intervals had been completed. Now let us define more functions to describe the photon's instantaneous velocity:

$$h(t) = (\cos_{xy}(f(t) * r + a) * \cos_{xz}(f(t) * r + a)) * C$$

$$g(t) = (\sin_{xy}(f(t) * r + a) * \cos_{xz}(f(t) * r + a)) * C$$

$$m(t) = (\cos_{xy}(f(t) * r + a) * \sin_{xz}(f(t) * r + a)) * C$$

Each function of these can be used to describe a point on a sphere's surface, we are using 2 circles to do this, one circle represents x and y, the other represents x and z. For example, at $\sin_{xy}(90)$, but the circle representing x and z, its radius would be 0, since the point is on the top of the sphere, and as you can see in each function, the angle is an output of $f(t)$ multiplied by the fixed rotation plus the initial angle.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{c} \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{t}{k}} h(n) * k \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{t}{k}} g(n) * K \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{t}{k}} m(n) * K \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\frac{t}{k}} \sqrt{(C * k)^2 - ((h(n) * k)^2 + (g(n) * k)^2 + (m(n) * k)^2) * k} \end{array} \right\}$$

This matrix represents a photon's position in all of these 4 dimensions: X,Y,Z,W. This is done by getting the instantaneous velocity of the photon at a specific point in time and multiplying it by k to simulate the photon moving for little time, and this is repeated $\frac{t}{k}$ times and summed to get the displacement for X,Y,Z,W.

2.2 Why would space bend the way it bends and why would this hypothesis' logic predict electromagnetic forces?

If we assume that each photon is like a fountain releasing quantum photons, these quantum photons also move at the speed of light, but they don't have real energy, they just move through space. Now let's imagine a charged elementary particle releasing quantum photons, to satisfy coulomb's law, these quantum photons will rotate at random intervals, but these intervals are mostly stable, meaning it is more likely that the interval changes by a small number than a big number

Thus it is more likely for a quantum photon to follow a path that satisfies coulomb's law, but how can it hold electromagnetic, or curvature energy? Well since all photons share 1 line, but not strictly due to the random rotation intervals, thus it affects other quantum photons' path.

There is no real line shared by all the photons, the closer they are to each other, the path becomes more "accurate". Now imagine 2 opposite charged elementary particles, now imagine a quantum photon from 1 of the charges approaching the opposite charge, since the quantum photon holds opposite curvature, the opposite charge's random intervals of rotation will change accordingly to the new path, thus the quantum photons released from that point is also released with a decreased starting curvature.

The thing is though, since quantum photons only move at the speed of light, there is a delay, thus relative to each charge, the other charge hasn't changed in position due to the delay, thus the path doesn't just reach a state of "equilibrium" due to the delay, thus they attract.

2.3 Why do elementary particles have inertia?

They don't have inertia, they just move at the speed of light in circles, and the reason the curvature doesn't like balance out on average, because for example if a car starts to move in circle by accelerating forwards, then decelerates, then accelerating backwards relative to the origin point, then decelerates, then accelerates forward again, it won't get behind the origin point, it would always be at the front of the origin point.

2.4 Extra

Now imagine an electron absorbing a photon, the photon isn't actually slowing down, instead it just moves in like zigzags due to the motion of the electron going in circles, and the electron's random rotation interval change according to the photon's path, thus it "reduces the lag" of the electron.

If we look at the proton's sub-atomic particles, there is a negative quark, but from a distance the proton is mostly perceived as a pure positive charge, since the paths for each quark's quantum photons meet, but at a lower distance, the paths get more chaotic since there is a lower chance for the paths to meet, thus explaining why an electron doesn't fully collide with the proton, since getting closer to the proton will only make paths more different than each others due to each quantum photon's perspective.

3 About the author

I'm an individual researcher interested in understanding the universe at a fundamental level, I hope you enjoyed my writing, I hope this will benefit you, and thank you for reading. :)